

AUTENTIK MATERIALLARNING ESP TALABALARI NUTQIY KO'NIKMALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI TA'SIRINI EKSPERIMENTAL O'RGANISH

Ziyodullayev Jamshid Azamat o'g'li, Jahon iqtisodiyoti va diplomatiya universiteti o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya

KIRISH: Maqolada kasbiy ingliz tili darslarida ESP (English for Specific Purposes – Maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili) talabalarini nutqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda autentik materiallarning samaradorligini o'rganishga qaratilgan tajriba-sinov ishlarini tashkil etish masalalari yoritilgan. Tajriba uch bosqichda amalga oshirilgan: tashkiliy tayyorgarlik, o'quv jarayonini joriy etish va natijalarni tahlil qilish. Tadqiqotda kasb-hunar texnologik kolleji ikkinchi bosqichida tahsil olayotgan 24 nafar talaba ishtirok etib, ular teng ravishda tajriba va nazorat guruhlariga ajratilgan. Tajriba guruhida amaliy ingliz tili mashg'ulotlariga ona tilida so'zlashuvchi ingliz tili vakillari tomonidan yaratilgan autentik tinglab tushunish materiallari joriy etilgan. Tadqiqotdan oldin talabalarning til o'rganish tajribasi, ehtiyojlari, munosabati va autentik materiallardan foydalanish darajasini aniqlash maqsadida so'rovnoma o'tkazilgan. Tanlangan metodologiya va o'quv dizayni autentik materiallarning ESP kontekstida kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishdagi pedagogik ahamiyatini aniqlashga qaratilgan.

MAQSAD: Mazkur tadqiqotning maqsadi kasbiy ta'lim muassasalarida tahsil olayotgan ESP talabalarining nutqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda autentik materiallarning samaradorligini aniqlashdan iborat. Tadqiqot autentik tinglab tushunish materiallarining talabalarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasi, nutq ravonligi, talaffuzi hamda kasbiy mulohazadagi ishonchini rivojlantirishga ta'sirini o'rganishga qaratilgan.

MATERIALLAR VA METODLAR: Tadqiqot kasb-hunar texnologik kollejining ikkinchi bosqichida tahsil olayotgan 24 nafar talaba ishtirokida o'tkazildi. Ishtirokchilar 12 nafardan tajriba va nazorat guruhlariga bo'lindi. Tajriba guruhining amaliy ingliz tili mashg'ulotlariga ingliz tilining ona tilida so'zlashuvchilari tomonidan tayyorlangan autentik audio va video materiallar kiritildi, nazorat guruhi esa an'anaviy darsliklar asosidagi ta'lim bilan shug'ullandi. Ma'lumotlar tajribadan oldingi va keyingi so'rovnoma, dars kuzatuvlari, nutqiy baholash ishlari hamda CEFR mezonlari asosidagi baholash vositalari orqali to'plandi. Talabalarning nutqiy ko'rsatkichlari va til o'rganishga bo'lgan munosabatlaridagi o'zgarishlarni aniqlash uchun miqdoriy va sifat tahlili usullaridan foydalanildi.

NATIJALAR VA MUHOKAMA: Tadqiqot natijalari autentik materiallardan foydalangan talabalar nazorat guruhidagi talabalarga nisbatan nutq ravonligi, talaffuz aniqligi, lug'at boyligi va kommunikativ ishonch jihatidan sezilarli darajada yaxshiroq natijalarga erishganligini ko'rsatdi. Autentik tinglab tushunish faoliyatlari talabalarga haqiqiy hayotiy til namunalari, turli aksentlarni hamda ularning kasbiy sohasiga mos kommunikatsiya uslublarini o'rganish imkonini berdi. So'rovnoma natijalari talabalarning autentik materiallardan foydalanishga nisbatan ijobiy munosabatda ekanligini ko'rsatdi, aksariyat ishtirokchilar darslarga bo'lgan qiziqish va motivatsiyaning ortganligini

ta'kidladilar. Muhokama qismida autentik resurslarni ESP ta'limiga integratsiya qilishning pedagogik afzalliklari va ularning sinfdagi ta'lim bilan real hayotdagi muloqot o'rtasidagi tafovutni kamaytirishdagi roli yoritilgan.

XULOSA: Tadqiqot natijalari autentik materiallar kasbiy ta'lim muassasalaridagi ESP talabalarining nutqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda samarali ta'lim vositasi ekanligini tasdiqladi. Ularning ingliz tili darslariga integratsiya qilinishi kommunikativ kompetensiyaning rivojlanishiga, talabalarining motivatsiyasi oshishiga hamda tabiiy til namunalari bilan ko'proq tanishishiga xizmat qiladi. Natijalar kasbiy ingliz tili o'qituvchilariga talabalarni kelajakdagi kasbiy va ish faoliyatidagi muloqotga samarali tayyorlash maqsadida autentik tinglab tushunish va gapirish faoliyatlarini o'quv jarayoniga kengroq joriy etishni tavsiya etadi. Kelgusida autentik materiallarning til kompetensiyasiga uzoq muddatli ta'sirini aniqlash uchun kattaroq tanlanma va uzoqroq tajriba davrini qamrab olgan tadqiqotlar o'tkazish maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Kalit so'zlar: autentik materiallar, ESP, kasbiy ta'lim, nutqiy ko'nikmalar, kommunikativ kompetensiya, tajriba-sinov ta'limi, ingliz tili darsi, autentik tinglab tushunish, so'rovnoma, til kompetensiyasi, kasb-hunar kolleji, CEFR.

ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ АУТЕНТИЧНЫХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ НА РАЗВИТИЕ НАВЫКОВ УСТНОЙ РЕЧИ У СТУДЕНТОВ ESP

Зиёдуллаев Жамшид Азамат угли, преподаватель Университета мировой экономики и дипломатии

Аннотация

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: В статье рассматривается организация экспериментального обучения, направленного на изучение эффективности аутентичных материалов в развитии навыков устной речи студентов ESP (English for Specific Purposes – английский язык для специальных целей) на занятиях по профессиональному английскому языку. Эксперимент проводился в три этапа: организационно-подготовительный этап, этап реализации учебного процесса и этап анализа результатов. В исследовании приняли участие 24 студента второго курса профессионального технологического колледжа, которые были поровну распределены на экспериментальную и контрольную группы. В занятия по практическому английскому языку для экспериментальной группы были интегрированы аутентичные аудиоматериалы, созданные носителями английского языка. До начала эксперимента были проведены анкетирования с целью выявления языкового опыта обучающихся, их потребностей, отношения к изучению языка и уровня знакомства с аутентичными материалами. Выбранная методология и учебный дизайн были направлены на определение педагогической ценности аутентичных материалов для развития коммуникативной компетенции в контексте обучения ESP.

ЦЕЛЬ: Цель данного исследования заключается в определении эффективности аутентичных материалов в развитии навыков устной речи студентов

ESP, обучающихся в учреждениях профессионального образования. Исследование направлено на изучение влияния аутентичных материалов для аудирования на развитие коммуникативной компетенции, беглости речи, произносительных навыков и уверенности обучающихся в профессиональном общении.

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ: Исследование проводилось с участием 24 студентов второго курса профессионального технологического колледжа. Участники были разделены на экспериментальную и контрольную группы по 12 человек в каждой. В учебный процесс экспериментальной группы были включены аутентичные аудио- и видеоматериалы, подготовленные носителями английского языка, тогда как контрольная группа обучалась по традиционной методике с использованием учебников. Сбор данных осуществлялся посредством анкетирования до и после эксперимента, наблюдения за учебным процессом, оценки навыков устной речи, а также на основе критериев оценивания, соответствующих общеевропейской системе CEFR. Для анализа изменений в речевых навыках студентов и их отношении к изучению языка применялись количественные и качественные методы исследования.

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ И ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ: Результаты исследования показали, что студенты, обучавшиеся с использованием аутентичных материалов, продемонстрировали более высокий уровень развития беглости речи, точности произношения, словарного запаса и коммуникативной уверенности по сравнению со студентами контрольной группы. Аутентичные задания по аудированию предоставили обучающимся возможность познакомиться с реальными образцами языка, различными акцентами и моделями профессионального общения, характерными для их будущей сферы деятельности. Результаты анкетирования свидетельствуют о положительном отношении студентов к использованию аутентичных материалов; большинство участников отметили повышение мотивации и заинтересованности в процессе обучения. В ходе обсуждения были выделены педагогические преимущества интеграции аутентичных ресурсов в обучение ESP и их роль в сокращении разрыва между учебной аудиторией и реальной коммуникативной практикой.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: Результаты исследования подтверждают, что аутентичные материалы являются эффективным инструментом обучения для развития навыков устной речи студентов ESP в системе профессионального образования. Их интеграция в процесс преподавания английского языка способствует развитию коммуникативной компетенции, повышению учебной мотивации и расширению контакта обучающихся с естественными языковыми образцами. Полученные результаты позволяют рекомендовать преподавателям профессионального английского языка более широко использовать аутентичные материалы для аудирования и говорения с целью подготовки студентов к эффективному профессиональному и деловому общению. В дальнейшем целесообразно проводить исследования с более широкой выборкой и увеличенной продолжительностью

эксперимента для изучения долгосрочного влияния аутентичных материалов на уровень владения языком.

Ключевые слова: аутентичные материалы, ESP, профессиональное образование, навыки устной речи, коммуникативная компетенция, экспериментальное обучение, урок английского языка, аутентичное аудирование, анкетирование, языковая компетенция, профессиональный колледж, CEFR.

AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE IMPACT OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF ESP STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS

Ziyodullayev Jamshid Azamat o'gli, Teacher of the University of World Economy and Diplomacy

Annotation

INTRODUCTION: the article outlines the organization of experimental teaching aimed at investigating the effectiveness of authentic materials in developing ESP students' speaking skills in vocational English classrooms. The experiment is implemented in three stages: organizational preparation, instructional implementation, and data analysis. The study involves 24 second-year students of a vocational technological college, divided equally into experimental and control groups. Authentic listening materials delivered by native speakers are integrated into Practical English lessons for the experimental group. Questionnaires are administered prior to the intervention to identify learners' backgrounds, attitudes, needs, and previous exposure to authentic materials. The selected methodology and instructional design aim to examine the pedagogical value of authentic materials for improving communicative competence in English for Specific Purposes contexts.

AIM: the aim of this study is to investigate the effectiveness of authentic materials in developing the speaking skills of ESP (English for Specific Purposes) students in vocational education settings. The research seeks to determine how authentic listening resources contribute to learners' communicative competence, speaking fluency, pronunciation, and confidence in professional communication contexts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: the study was conducted with 24 second-year students enrolled in a vocational technological college. Participants were divided into an experimental group (12 students) and a control group (12 students). Authentic audio and video materials produced by native English speakers were integrated into Practical English lessons for the experimental group, while the control group received conventional instruction using textbook-based materials. Data were collected through pre- and post-intervention questionnaires, classroom observations, speaking assessments, and CEFR-aligned evaluation criteria. Quantitative and qualitative analyses were employed to measure changes in students' speaking performance and attitudes toward language learning.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: the findings revealed that students exposed to authentic materials demonstrated noticeable improvement in speaking fluency,

pronunciation accuracy, vocabulary acquisition, and communicative confidence compared to those in the control group. Authentic listening activities provided learners with opportunities to encounter real-life language use, various accents, and professional communication patterns relevant to their vocational fields. Questionnaire results indicated positive learner attitudes toward the use of authentic materials, with most participants reporting increased motivation and engagement during lessons. The discussion highlights the pedagogical benefits of integrating authentic resources into ESP instruction and emphasizes their role in bridging the gap between classroom learning and real-world communication.

CONCLUSION: the study confirms that authentic materials are an effective instructional tool for enhancing ESP students' speaking skills in vocational education. Their integration into English language instruction contributes to the development of communicative competence, increases learner motivation, and promotes greater exposure to natural language use. The results suggest that vocational English teachers should incorporate authentic listening and speaking activities into their teaching practices to better prepare students for professional and workplace communication. Further research with larger samples and extended intervention periods is recommended to explore the long-term impact of authentic materials on language proficiency.

Keywords: authentic materials, ESP, vocational education, speaking skills, communicative competence, experimental teaching, English classroom, authentic listening, questionnaire, language proficiency, vocational college, CEFR.

Nowadays, the ability to communicate effectively in English is regarded as one of the essential requirements for students of vocational educational institutions. In the context of globalization and rapid technological development, learners are expected to possess not only theoretical knowledge of English grammar and vocabulary, but also practical communicative skills related to their professional fields. Therefore, the issue of developing communicative competence in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) classrooms has become one of the significant concerns of modern language teaching. Despite the growing interest in authenticity in language teaching, the use of authentic materials in vocational ESP classrooms still requires further investigation, particularly in the context of vocational education. The present study focuses on examining the role of authentic listening materials in developing ESP students' speaking skills in English classrooms. It is aimed to identify whether the integration of authentic sources into Practical English lessons can positively influence learners' communicative competence and promote greater confidence in spoken interaction.

To achieve this objective, experimental teaching involving vocational college students was organized using authentic listening materials accompanied by speaking activities designed in accordance with learners' professional needs and language level. The study

analyzes the organization of the experimental teaching process and discusses the obtained results concerning the development of students' listening and speaking skills.

The process of conducting the experiment. The experiment was organized in three stages:

1. Organizational stage: a) diagnostics; b) determination of the aim and objectives of the experiment; c) selection of authentic materials and design of activities.
2. Implementation stage.
3. Experimental teaching data analysis.

The aim of the experiment was to determine whether authentic sources could effectively contribute to the improvement of ESP students' speaking skills in vocational colleges.

The participants of the study were second-year students of the Vocational Technological College named after Mirzo Ulug'bek. English is not the major subject in this institution, as greater emphasis is placed on disciplines such as physics, chemistry, and biology. Students study English primarily to develop the ability to communicate within the scope of their future professional fields, including oil and grain products, culinary studies, and computer technology. In addition, they are expected to acquire knowledge of Technical English in order to function successfully in these areas. Alongside students' academic specialization, other variables including age, gender, and language background were also taken into consideration as relevant factors of the experiment.

The participants ranged in age from 16 to 17 years. According to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), their level of English language proficiency corresponded to the B1 level. The majority of the participants represented Uzbek cultural and linguistic backgrounds.

The experiment involved two groups of college students comprising a total of 24 participants. No differences existed in terms of group size, as both the experimental group (EG) and the control group (CG) consisted of 12 students each.

Practical English lessons based on authentic materials were conducted during scientific-pedagogical practice. The participants were exposed to authentic listening materials presented by native speakers of English during these lessons.

Prior to the implementation of practical ESP lessons, pre-questionnaires were administered to the students of the target groups. According to the responses provided by the majority of the participants, they had had little or no previous exposure to authentic materials in their earlier learning experience.

The use of questionnaires is one of the most common research methods, as it enables the collection of a large amount of information concerning various issues such as communication difficulties, preferred learning styles, classroom activity preferences, attitudes, and beliefs (Richards, 2001). In the context of the present study, questionnaires were initially employed to elicit information about learners' attitudes toward the course and their expectations regarding what they intended to learn before the completion of the semester. The content of the questionnaire is of considerable

importance for course design, as it directly influences the extent to which learners' actual needs can be identified.

The experimental teaching involved authentic listening materials (selected from *Authentic Listening Resource Pack* by Mark Hancock and Annie McDonald, 2015), radio podcasts, pre-, while-, and post-listening worksheets, as well as pre- and post-tests. These materials were selected to provide meaningful and relevant data appropriate to the objectives of the research.

Most of the teaching materials, particularly listening activities, were organized according to a clear instructional pattern. They were intended to develop ESP students' language proficiency in the target language, more specifically, their listening skills. Although authentic listening sources and pre-listening, while-listening, and post-listening activities were selected from different sources, speaking activities based on the authentic listening materials were specifically designed for the purposes of the study.

The selection of authentic listening materials was based on predetermined criteria. Several important factors were taken into consideration, including the relevance of the materials to learners' needs and proficiency levels, their appropriateness to the course objectives, their skill-oriented nature, their potential to engage learners' interest, and their degree of informativeness.

The speaking activities encouraged learners to produce a greater number of utterances related to their professional fields and promoted more confident classroom communication. Redundancy and unnecessary repetition in students' communicative performance were gradually reduced, while expressions used by native speakers in the listening materials began to be reflected in learners' oral production.

As mentioned previously, authentic materials were selected according to established criteria. The topics presented in these listening materials covered a range of areas, including everyday communication such as giving instructions, providing recommendations, telephone conversations, news podcasts, and similar issues. The listening sources contained both linguistic and cultural content, various samples of English varieties, and authentic expressions appropriate to the B1 level. The materials were presented in segments, allowing learners sufficient time to comprehend the content and complete the assigned tasks. These materials were selected to provide learners with appropriate vocabulary related to their professional fields, enabling them to improve their ability to build conversations connected with their areas of specialization in English.

Pre-experiment tests were employed to obtain data on learners' listening comprehension and speaking abilities in English. Both pre-experiment and post-experiment tests were administered to assess students' language skills and to observe the improvements achieved during the course of the study. The listening tests consisted of various task types, including multiple-choice questions, matching tasks, gap-filling exercises, and short-answer questions. The pre-test provided baseline data for comparison with the results obtained at the end of the study. In addition, a final test was conducted following the completion of the experimental teaching in order to obtain comprehensive data on learners' progress. This test included multiple-choice questions

as well as gap-filling tasks and was intended to generate the data required to address the objectives of the study.

The measures employed in the research were considered valid and reliable according to several criteria. These included the direct correspondence between scoring procedures and the constructs being measured, a sufficient number of task and structure samples, unambiguous test items, clear and comprehensible instructions, as well as a legible and non-distracting layout. Furthermore, the results obtained from these measures provided relevant data for further analysis of the research outcomes.

The equipment used in the study included a laptop, personal computer, overhead projector (OHP), speakers, and discs. Computer equipment was used to play authentic listening tracks so that students could complete the listening tasks effectively. The overhead projector was utilized to display selected written tasks designed for speaking activities.

According to the results of the pre-questionnaire, the participants had little or no prior experience with authentic materials. Therefore, general explanations regarding the concept of authentic sources were provided to establish a basic understanding of authenticity among the learners. After completing several listening activities, students began to participate more actively in the study process by asking questions about the topics and attempting to express their opinions using vocabulary derived from the listening extracts. This process enabled them to engage in communication in the target language more confidently than before.

Participants were informed that active involvement in the study process could contribute to the improvement of their English language skills. Their primary tasks involved listening to authentic input and completing practical activities related to the presented materials. The instructional sessions lasted two hours and were conducted twice a week over a six-week period during scientific-pedagogical practice.

As one of the primary objectives of the research was to determine whether authentic materials could enhance students' motivation, learners' attitudes towards the presented materials were regularly observed. The learners tended to discuss certain essential or interesting parts of the listening tracks. Therefore, after completing the assigned activities, the listening track was replayed, and students were encouraged to express their opinions on the topic. The process was organized in the form of discussions in which each student had the opportunity to contribute their views. Finally, learners were given different tasks in which they were required to work in pairs or groups and create conversations involving two or more participants. The remainder of the study followed a similar pattern, although different activities such as role-plays, debates, discussions, and detailed descriptions were also employed.

At the end of the experiment, students took a final test in order to compare their results with the initial performance. In addition, learners participated in short interviews with the researcher, during which they expressed their attitudes towards the teaching process and the overall organization of the lessons. The members of the experimental group provided generally positive feedback and stated that the use of authentic materials

significantly supported their involvement in the learning process. They also expressed the hope that this approach would be applied in their future academic studies.

The data collection process of the present study lasted for six weeks. However, prior to the implementation phase, a considerable amount of time was devoted to the preparation of materials and research instruments.

It should be noted that the members of the experimental group took the final test first, as they were still attending lessons at that time. Nevertheless, due to the researcher's efforts to complete the study, the control group also met and completed the test. Subsequently, all relevant results were collected for comparison. The pre-test results were compared with the post-test results, and average scores were calculated. After collecting all necessary data, the analysis and interpretation phase was conducted. All results were processed, analyzed, and organized into several tables and charts for comparison purposes.

The results and findings. The study involved two stages of testing: pre-experimental and post-experimental tests. According to the State Educational Standards of Uzbekistan, college students are required to reach B1 level in accordance with the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). Therefore, pre-experimental listening and speaking tests were administered at the target level in order to collect data on students' language proficiency prior to the implementation of practical teaching.

The results of the listening test indicated that students' listening skills were lower than expected. In fact, it was anticipated that students would achieve approximately 80% task completion; however, the actual result was 60% according to the test outcomes.

Afterwards, a speaking test was conducted based on the content of the listening tasks in order to identify learners' level of communicative competence. In line with this procedure, speaking assessment criteria were developed in accordance with the requirements stated in the State Educational Standards (see Appendix). The topics were selected in accordance with the course syllabus and students' professional orientation.

It should be noted that everyday communicative situations, including giving instructions, describing professional fields, providing suggestions, and similar tasks, were taken into consideration during the design of the speaking test. After all relevant data had been collected, it was carefully analyzed in order to reach a valid conclusion regarding the participants' level of proficiency.

All results obtained from the pre-experimental and post-experimental tests were systematically analyzed. The data were examined from two perspectives in order to ensure the reliability and validity of the research findings. The pre-test results, which were used to determine participants' initial listening and speaking skills, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Pre-experiment Test Results of the level of language performance in listening and speaking

The number of students	Listening skills (%)	Speaking skills (%)
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24	60 %	65 %
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During the pre-experimental stage, a frequency distribution chart was constructed to summarize the pre-test data and to clearly identify how many participants demonstrated similar levels of performance, as well as to determine the range of their responses and overall performance distribution.

Figure 1. Experimental Group’s Pre-Experiment Speaking Test Results (Frequency Distribution)

Let us consider the Experimental Group’s pre-experimental speaking test results presented in the frequency distribution (Figure 1). As can be seen from the chart, students’ scores on the speaking task ranged between 52 and 69, with several identical values occurring in some cases. The presence of variation in scores indicates heterogeneity among the participants, which contributes to the reliability of the results and allows the researcher to examine how the hypothesis of the study applies to learners with different initial levels of proficiency. The main tendency observed in the figure shows that most of the identical results were concentrated in the middle of the score range, which suggests that the selection of participants was appropriate and that a number of students were at an average level of language performance at the beginning of the study.

During the test procedure, most students experienced difficulties with the listening task and requested that the recording be replayed. However, this was not allowed, as it could have influenced the validity of the research results. The main reason for students’ weak listening performance was their limited experience with authentic listening tasks in previous lessons. Although they had some practice with adapted listening materials, as

indicated in the course syllabus, they had not been exposed to authentic native speaker speech.

Despite these difficulties, a slight improvement in speaking performance was observed, and students' speaking skills demonstrated relatively better progress compared to listening skills.

After identifying students' initial level of proficiency in listening and speaking, the participants were divided into experimental (EG) and control (CG) groups. In the process of grouping, care was taken to ensure comparable proficiency levels across both groups. More specifically, the eight strongest students were evenly distributed between the two groups (four students in the CG and four in the EG). After several instructional sessions with the experimental group, while the control group continued studying with adapted materials, a post-test was administered to both groups in order to compare the results with the pre-test data.

Post-experiment test results of both groups are provided in Table 2.

Table 2.

Groups and number of students	Listening skills (%)	Speaking skills (%)
EG - 12	70%	78 %
CG - 12	63 %	67%

The experimental group's test results on speaking after experimental teaching is presented with frequency distribution.

Figure 2. Experimental Group's Post-Experiment Speaking Test Results (Frequency Distribution)

It is evident from the chart that students' scores in completing speaking tasks ranged between 65 and 83, with several identical values occurring at certain points. In comparison with the chart presenting the pre-experimental speaking test results, the statistics indicate that students' overall performance in speaking tasks improved by approximately 13% after the experimental teaching. The main tendency of the figure also shows that most identical results were concentrated in the middle of the score range. In fact, the chart provides evidence for the conclusion that vocational college students who participated in the experimental teaching made noticeable progress in improving their language proficiency, more specifically their speaking skills, after receiving a series of practical English lessons based on authentic listening materials.

As previously mentioned, a clear improvement in the language proficiency of experimental group (EG) students can be observed from the presented data. This suggests development in both speaking and listening skills among the majority of EG participants compared to the pre-experimental test results. Moreover, the number of students whose performance improved also increased.

In order to present a clearer overview of the pre-experimental and post-experimental test results, the data were summarized in a single table. This allows for a direct comparison of both sets of results and facilitates the drawing of meaningful conclusions regarding the effectiveness of the experimental teaching, which is closely associated with the use of authentic materials in the teaching process.

Table 3. Results of Pre and Post-Experiment Tests of Experimental and Control Groups of the Level of Language Performance (listening and speaking)

Experimental teaching (ET)	Groups and number of students	Listening skills (%)	Speaking skills (%)
Pre – ET	EG - 12	60 %	65%
Post – ET	EG - 12	70%	78 %
Pre – ET	CG - 12	60 %	65%
Post – ET	CG - 12	63 %	67%

It can be clearly observed from Table 3 that, in comparison with the experimental group, the control group results do not show any significant difference from the pre-experimental test results. The control group did not receive exposure to authentic listening materials during the main phase of the study, which allows the assumption that the use of authentic listening materials in the English classroom contributes to the development of EFL learners' communicative competence. Through listening tasks based on authentic materials, a steady improvement in the experimental group's speaking skills can be observed in the post-test results compared to those of the control group. In fact, authentic listening materials, along with speaking tasks designed on their basis, contributed to the development of students' communicative competence.

Progress in the experimental group compared to the control group was also observed in listening skills development. All 12 participants in the experimental group demonstrated improvement in the listening section of the post-experimental test compared to their pre-experimental results. Moreover, the differences between the pre- and post-test scores indicate that the level of improvement was considerable.

Another factor contributing to the validity of the findings is the comparison of pre- and post-test results across both the experimental and control groups, which were obtained during the study.

Following the experimental teaching, a survey was conducted among English language teachers (n=5) and students (n=15). Participants were asked to express their opinions regarding the effectiveness of authentic materials in ESP lessons and to evaluate them as instructional tools. Teachers and students were required to rate the given statements using a five-point Likert scale: 1 – completely disagree; 2 – disagree; 3 – partially agree; 4 – agree; and 5 – strongly agree (see Appendix). For reporting purposes, the scale was further converted into a qualitative classification: 1 – Very poor, 2 – Poor; 3 – Average; 4 – Very good; and 5 – Excellent. All responses were collected anonymously to ensure that participants could provide honest and unbiased feedback.

Table 4. Evaluated aspect

Evaluated Aspects	Percentage of teachers and students who ranked the aspect as <i>Very good</i> and <i>Excellent</i> .
Opportunities provided by the materials to listen to authentic English (only the teachers' evaluation)	100
Opportunities motivated the students' activity during the lesson.	88
Opportunities provided by authentic listening materials to enlarge vocabulary.	84
Overall perception of the effect of the materials in the English classrooms.	86
Positive effects of authentic tasks on developing communicative competence	93

The evaluated aspects included teachers' and students' views on the opportunities provided through the instructional process and the extent of benefit they derived from the presented materials, activities, and tasks. Table 3 presents the evaluated aspects and the percentage of teachers and students who rated each aspect positively. During the survey, both teachers and students were asked to evaluate the course materials objectively in order to ensure the reliability of the collected data. The survey results were summarized and presented in terms of the percentages of "Very good" and "Excellent" responses. Having completed this task, participants expressed

their opinions regarding the effectiveness of the listening materials used during English classes. According to informal interviews conducted with the participants, the listening materials provided opportunities to acquire important vocabulary related to their field of study and professional areas. In addition, various types of speaking activities implemented during the lessons were found to be engaging and contributed to increasing students' motivation to learn English more effectively.

Conclusion. The present study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of authentic materials in developing ESP students' speaking skills in vocational college classrooms. The experimental teaching was organized in three stages, including the organizational phase, the implementation stage, and the analysis of the obtained data. The results of the study demonstrated that the use of authentic materials had a positive influence on students' language development, particularly in listening comprehension and speaking skills.

The comparison of pre-experimental and post-experimental test results showed that the experimental group achieved noticeable progress after the intervention, whereas the control group did not demonstrate significant changes. It was observed that students who were exposed to authentic listening materials became more confident in speaking activities and showed improvement in using vocabulary related to their professional fields. In addition, learners gradually reduced their dependence on memorized expressions and adapted more naturally to communicative tasks. This suggests that authentic materials not only support language input but also contribute to the development of productive skills in ESP contexts.

The results of questionnaires and informal interviews also confirmed that authentic materials had a positive effect on learners' motivation. The majority of students reported that lessons based on authentic listening sources were more interesting and engaging compared to traditional classroom materials. It was also noted that students became more active during discussions and showed greater willingness to participate in speaking tasks. Teachers involved in the survey also evaluated the materials positively, emphasizing their practical value and relevance to students' professional needs.

Another important finding of the study is that authentic materials helped to bridge the gap between classroom English and real-life language use. Exposure to native speaker speech, different accents, and natural expressions enabled students to develop better listening awareness and improved their ability to respond in communicative situations. At the same time, the effectiveness of these materials largely depended on their careful selection, adaptation, and integration into the lesson structure, taking into account students' proficiency level and learning objectives.

Overall, it can be concluded that the use of authentic materials is an effective pedagogical approach in ESP teaching, especially in vocational education contexts where learners require practical communicative competence for future professional activities. The findings of the study support the idea that authentic input can significantly contribute to both linguistic development and learner motivation when systematically incorporated into classroom practice.

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